

Optical Activity of Alkaloid Salts of Geometrically Isomeric Unsaturated Acids.

BY PANCHANAN NEOGI AND ANIL BHUSAN SEN-GUPTA.

The relation between geometrical isomerism and optical activity was first studied by Walden (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1896, 20, 377) who observed that in the case of diamyl esters of maleic and fumaric acids, chloro- and bromomaleic and chloro- and bromofumaric acids the fumaroid possessed the greater rotatory power, but Hartwall (Dissertation, Helsingfors, 1904) found the reverse rule to hold for the acid and neutral bornyl esters of maleic and fumaric acids, although with both menthyl and bornyl acid citraconates and mesaconates the fumaroid possessed greater rotatory effect.

Hilditch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 61, 704) from a study of several alkaloid salts (conine, codeine, brucine and cinchonine) of maleic and fumaric acids obtained results in chloroform solutions which with some few exceptions showed that the malenoid forms had greater specific rotations than the fumaroid.

It appeared to us that a larger amount of experimental work should be forthcoming to establish, if possible, a general rule regarding the relative optical activity of active geometrical isomers and therefore, we undertook a systematic study of the rotations of a large number of alkaloid salts of ethylinic dicarboxylic acids.

The alkaloids used in the work described were quinine, brucine, quinidine, strychnine and cinchonidine, and the rotatory power of the salts of these with maleic and fumaric acids, citraconic and mesaconic as well as crotonic and isocrotonic acids has been measured. The solvent generally employed was dry alcohol, in a few cases it was necessary to have recourse to chloroform. Owing to the great ionising influence of water, aqueous solutions were not employed.

It appears from the present investigation that in the case of alkaloid salts of unsaturated isomeric ethylinic acids it can be formulated as a general rule that *the specific rotations of the malenoid type is almost always greater*, bearing some exceptions observed by

Hilditch (*loc. cit.*), than that of the fumaroid form and that the specific rotations of the alkaloid salts and amyl esters of the ethylinic dicarboxylic acids are relatively reverse of each other. So far as the effect of dilution is concerned it is of interest to note that with increase in dilution the specific rotation decreases. The rotations were obtained in non-ionising media, *viz.*, alcoholic and chloroformic solution and hence it is not strange if reverse results are obtained to those of Oudemans and Landolt (*Annalen*, 1876, 182, 33, 58; *Ber.*, 1873, 6, 1077) who showed that in ionising media such as in aqueous solutions the rotations increased and were approximating those of the active ions on continuous dilution owing to ionisation.

The influence of solvents on optical activity has been studied by many investigators and various theories have been put forward to explain the anomalous behaviour of rotations in different solvents. But so far as the effect of concentration on rotation is concerned no satisfactory explanation is found in literature. Graham (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 746), who has shown that Oudemans-Landolt law is not universally applicable, suggested that the change observed was not dependent on the electrolytic dissociation alone but depended principally on the character of the metallic atom or electropositive grouping, since similar effects were produced by members of the same group in the periodic table. Armstrong and Walker (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1913 88A, 388) are of opinion that the cause of the variation in the optical rotatory power of organic compounds and anomalous rotatory dispersion may be ascribed to (a) alteration in the molecular size and to the formation of compounds between solvents and the solute, (b) to the occurrence of change giving rise to the presence of reversibly related isodynamic forms.

The decrease of the specific rotations of the salts with increase in dilution in non-ionising media might be supposed to be due to the formation of some compounds of the solute with the solvent employed, and that with increase in dilution the proportion of the molecules existing in the combining state increases thus causing a diminution in the proportions of active molecules. It was not possible to have direct evidence in support of this view by determining the molecular weight of the salt at different concentrations in alcoholic or chloroformic solution by the freezing point method owing to very low freezing point of alcohol or chloroform. The boiling point method is obviously inapplicable owing to possibility of decomposition. The substances are insoluble in benzene. The

suggestion, therefore, remains a tentative one so long as direct evidence is not forthcoming.

No generalisation as regards the magnitude of the increase of the specific rotations of the malenoid type over the fumaroid form is possible. In most cases, however, using maleic and fumaric acids the increase is between five to ten degrees, in the case of citraconates and mesaconates the increase is between three to twelve degrees, and finally in the case of crotonates and isocrotonates it is between four to seven degrees. This is only a rough approximation as individual variations in equal dilutions are sometimes besides the limit mentioned above.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General method of the preparation of the salts.—Alcoholic solutions of the base (2 mol.) and the acid (1 mol.) were mixed together and allowed to evaporate slowly, when solid crystals separated. The crystals were filtered and purified by washing with hot acetone in which the alkaloids and the acids were soluble but the salts insoluble. The salts were finally recrystallised from hot alcohol or water as colourless needles.

The isomeric salts differ from each other in melting points, solubility and sometimes in the shape of crystals.

The salts decolourise rapidly dilute permanganate solution and bromine water, thus showing the presence of unsaturation. They are insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution (hot or cold) proving the absence of free carboxyl group and all of them are neutral to litmus paper showing the formation of dialkaloidal salts. The alkaloidal salts are described in Table I.

Alcoholic solutions of the same concentration of the isomeric salts were prepared and the rotations were measured in a 2 dcm. tube keeping the temperature constant by circulating water at constant temperature through the tube. From the rotations thus observed the specific rotations were calculated. The rotations at different dilution are given in Table II.

TABLE I.

Name.	Formula	M. p.	Found	Analysis.	Calc.
Diquinine maleate	$(C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_2)_2C_4H_4O_4$	182-83°	C, 68.79; H, 7.11; N, 7.59		C, 69.1; H, 6.8; N, 7.32
Diquinine fumarate	"	187-88°	C, 68.82; H, 7.01; N, 7.48		"
Dicinchonidine maleate	$(C_{19}H_{22}N_2O)_2C_4H_4O_4$	182°	C, 71.24; H, 7.13; N, 8.07		C, 71.59; H, 6.81; N, 7.96
Dicinchonidine fumarate	"	186	C, 71.31; H, 7.21; N, 8.18		"
Distrychnine maleate	$(C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_2)_2C_4H_4O_4, 2H_2O$	210°	C, 66.91; H, 6.62; N, 7.18; H ₂ O, 4.15		C, 67.31; H, 6.34; N, 6.88; H ₂ O, 4.39
Distrychnine fumarate	$(C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_2)_2C_4H_4O_4, 4H_2O$	240°	C, 64.02; H, 6.88; N, 6.87; H ₂ O, 8.12		C, 64.48; H, 6.54; N, 6.54; H ₂ O, 8.1
Diquinidine maleate	$(C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_2)_2C_4H_4O_4$	98-99°	C, 68.67; H, 7.32; N, 7.67		C, 69.1; H, 6.8; N, 7.32
Diquinidine fumarate	"	154°	C, 68.82; H, 7.14; N, 7.45		"
Brucine mesaconate	$(C_{23}H_{26}N_2O_4)_2C_5H_6O_4, 5H_2O$	205-07°	C, 60.41; H, 6.85; N, 5.72; H ₂ O, 8.5		C, 60.7; H, 6.74; N, 5.5; H ₂ O, 8.9
Brucine citraconate	$(C_{23}H_{26}N_2O_4)_2C_5H_6O_4, 4H_2O$	209-10°	C, 61.34; H, 6.8; N, 5.97; H ₂ O, 6.8		C, 61.8; H, 6.6; N, 5.65; H ₂ O, 7.2

Dicinchonidine mesaconate	$(C_{19}H_{22}N_2O)_2C_6H_6O_4$	216-17°	C, 70.63; H, 7.14; N, 7.91	C, 70.86; H, 6.96; N, 7.79
Dicinchonidine citraconate	"	173-75°	C, 70.56; H, 7.25; N, 8.14	"
Strychnine crotonate	$(C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_2)C_4H_6O_2$	215-17°	C, 71.01; H, 6.79; N, 6.83	C, 71.42; H, 6.6; N, 6.6
Strychnine isocrotonate	"	250-52°	C, 70.87; H, 6.8; N, 6.93	"
Quinine crotonate	$(C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_2)C_4H_6O_2$	*136°	C, 69.9; H, 7.6; N, 7.08	C, 70.24; H, 7.31; N, 6.82
Quinine isocrotonate	"	*160-162°	C, 69.74; H, 7.41; N, 7.14	"
Distrychnine mesaconate	$(C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_2)_2C_6H_6O_4 \cdot 3H_2O$	280°	C, 65.67; H, 6.73; N, 6.69; H ₂ O, 6.02	C, 66.1; H, 6.57; N, 6.57; H ₂ O, 6.02
Distrychnine citraconate	$(C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_2)_2C_6H_6O_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	*185°	C, 67.39; H, 6.62; N, 6.9; H ₂ O, 3.86	C, 67.62; H, 6.47; N, 6.71; H ₂ O, 3.81
Diquinine mesaconate	$(C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_2)_2C_6H_6O_4$	215-16°	C, 69.6; H, 7.03; N, 7.28	C, 69.41; H, 6.9; N, 7.19
Diquinine citraconate	"	*96-98°	C, 69.15; H, 7.2; N, 7.31	"

* Refers to m. p. without decomposition, the rest melt with decomposition.

TABLE II.

Temp. 31°.		<i>Diquinine maleate</i>				<i>Diquinine fumarate</i>			
Conc. per 100 c. c.	Actual rotation.	Specific rotation.	Molecular rotation.	Actual rotation.	Specific rotation.	Molecular rotation.			
0·9440 g.	2·474°	-131·03°	-1001·06°	2·398°	-127·09°	-960·9°			
0·4720	1·181	-125·10	-949·3	1·146	-121·39	-927·4			
0·2560	0·441	-93·43	-710·13	0·391	-82·83	-631·8			
0·1180	0·189	-80·08	-612·1	0·171	-72·45	-593·9			
Temp. 30°.		<i>Dicinchonidine maleate</i>				<i>Dicinchonidine fumarate</i>			
1·3312	2·815	-105·73	-744·3	2·642	-99·28	-698·57			
0·3328	0·663	-99·6	-701·18	0·609	-91·4	-643·4			
0·1664	0·285	-85·64	-603·9	0·264	-79·2	-558·5			
0·0832	0·134	-80·52	-564·3	0·128	-73·9	-520·5			
Temp. 24°.		<i>Distrychnine maleate</i>				<i>Distrychnine fumarate</i>			
1·084	0·912	-42·06	-344·8	0·846	-39·02	-334·01			
0·542	0·405	-37·18	-304·8	0·35	-32·28	-276·3			
0·271	0·187	-34·5	-282·9	0·16	-29·52	-252·6			
0·1355	0·085	-31·36	-257·15	0·069	-25·46	-217·9			

Temp. 30°.		<i>Diquinidine maleate</i>			<i>Diquinidine fumarate</i>		
Conc. per 100 c. c.	Actual rotation.	Specific rotation.	Molecular rotation.	Actual rotation.	Specific rotation.	Molecular rotation.	
1.2544 g.	5.27	210.06	1604.85	5.225	208.26	1591.1	
0.6272	2.61	208.05	1589.5	2.582	205.8	1572.3	
0.3136	1.28	204.08	1559.17	1.25	199.29	1522.5	
Temp. 24°.		<i>Brucine citraconate</i>			<i>Brucine mesaconate</i>		
1.6816	1.295	-38.5	-388.08	1.136	-33.78	-334.4	
0.8408	0.585	-34.79	-1050.68	0.510	-30.32	-300.16	
0.4204	0.240	-28.34	-285.66	0.217	-25.8	-255.42	
Temp. 30°.		<i>Cinchonidine citraconate</i>			<i>Cinchonidine mesaconate</i>		
2	3.95	-98.75	-709.02	3.66	-91.5	-656.9	
1	1.75	-87.5	-628.25	1.65	-82.5	-592.35	
0.8	1.304	-81.5	-585.17	0.698	-69.8	-501.16	
0.5	0.75	-75	-538.5	0.502	-62.75	-486.44	
0.4	0.541	-67.66	-485.79	0.215	-53.75	-385.92	
0.2	0.239	-59.65	-429.7	1.27	-79.3	-569.37	

TABLE II (continued).

Temp. 30°.		* <i>Strychnine crotonate</i>		* <i>Strychnine isocrotonate</i>	
Conc. per 100 c. c.	Actual rotation.	Specific rotation.	Molecular rotation.	Actual rotation.	Specific rotation.
1.22 g.	1.23	-50.4	-211.68	1.15	-46.3
0.61	0.597	-44.01	-184.84	0.492	-40.3
0.305	0.24	-39.34	-165.22	0.198	-32.45
Temp. 31°.		<i>Quinine crotonate</i>		<i>Quinine isocrotonate</i>	
1.2	2.99	-124.58	-510.77	2.845	-118.5
0.6	1.40	-116.6	-478.06	1.31	-109.16
0.3	0.64	-106.6	-487.06	0.6	-100.05
0.15	0.29	-96.6	-396.06	0.272	-90.65
Temp. 30°.		<i>Distrychnine citraconate</i>		<i>Distrychnine mesaconate</i>	
1.144	1.315	-57.47	-458.6	1.162	-50.78
0.572	0.612	-53.4	-426.13	0.48	-41.95
0.286	0.268	-46.9	-374.26	0.21	-36.71
0.143	0.109	-38.1	-304.03	0.082	-28.6

* Rotation was observed in chloroform solution.

Temp. 30°.	<i>Diquinine citraconate</i>				<i>Diquinine mesaconate</i>			
	Conc. per 100 c. c.	Actual rotation.	Specific rotation.	Molecular rotation.	Actual rotation.	Specific rotation.	Molecular rotation.	
1.252 g.	3.292	-131.4	-1022.29	3.195	-127.6	-992.72		
0.626	1.561	-124.68	-970.01	1.525	-121.8	-947.6		
0.313	0.7234	-115.5	-898.59	0.661	-105.5	-820.79		
0.1565	0.287	-91.7	-713.42	2.266	-84.98	-661.14		

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE, CALCUTTA.

Received March 8, 1933.

